

Synthesis, spectral and antimicrobial studies of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes with a nitrogen donor new azamacrocyclic ligand with pendent arms

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Abstract : The complexes of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} were synthesized with the new azamacrocyclic ligand. The ligand [1,5,8,12-tetraaza-3,10-diethyl-2,4,9,11-tetramethyl-6(7),13(14)-di(bromopyridine)] was prepared by the reaction of 3-ethyl-2,4-pentadione and 5-bromo-2,6-diaminopyridine. All the complexes have been found to have general composition [M(L)X₂] [where M = Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} and X = Cl⁻, NO₃⁻, 1/2SO₄²⁻]. All the complexes are characterized by the conductance measurements, magnetic susceptibility measurements, mass, IR and electronic spectral studies. An octahedral geometry was assigned for Ni^{II} complexes and tetragonal for Cu^{II} complexes. The biological actions of the ligand and complexes have been screened *in vitro* against different pathogenic fungi and several bacteria to study their comparative capacity to inhibit the growth.

Keywords : Spectroscopic, EPR, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, 5-bromo-2,3-diaminopyridine, 3-ethyl-2,4-pentadione.

Introduction

Transition metal macrocyclic complexes are of great significance on account of their unique coordination and structural properties, their utilities as bio-inorganic models¹⁻⁵. These chelating molecules are also of importance, because they are capable of furnishing an environment of controlled geometry and ligand-field strength. Due to their electronic, magnetic and electrochemical properties the corresponding metal ions also play an important role in a number of activities. The vast family of macrocyclic ligands has now been established as an integral part of the general field of coordination chemistry. In recent years, functionalized pendent arm macrocyclic complexes have been designed and prepared so as to mimic the structure and properties of certain metalloenzymes and metalloprotein⁶⁻¹⁵.

In view of the above in the present paper we report the synthesis and spectroscopic characterization of macrocyclic complexes of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with a nitrogen donor macrocyclic ligand. The antimicrobial studies of these complexes have also been reported.

Experimental

All the chemical used were of AR grade and procured from Fluka and Sigma Aldrich. Metals salts were purchased from E. Merck and were used as received.

Preparation of ligand :

The hot ethanolic solution (20 mL) of 5-bromo-2,3-diaminopyridine (3.76 g, 0.02 mol) and the hot ethanolic solution (20 mL) of 3-ethyl-2,4-pentadione (2.56 mL, 0.02 mol) were mixed slowly with constant stirring. This mixture was refluxed at (80–90 °C) for 6–8 h (pH 4–5) in the presence of few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid. On cooling light yellowish Heena green coloured precipitate was formed, which was filtered, washed and dried under vacuum over P₄O₁₀, yield 54%, m.p. 180 °C. The elemental analysis found (found atomic mass 558 amu), C, 51.48; H, 5.04 and N, 15.60% calculated for C₂₄H₂₈N₆Br₂ (calculated atomic mass 560 amu), C, 51.42; H, 5.00 and N, 15.00%.

Preparation of complexes :

Hot ethanolic (20 mL) solution of ligand (0.560 g, 0.001 mol) and hot ethanolic solution of corresponding

Fig. 1

metal salts (0.001 mol) were mixed together with constant stirring. The mixture was refluxed for 5–7 h at 70–90 °C. On cooling coloured complex was precipitated out. It was filtered washed with cold EtOH and dried under vacuum over P_4O_{10} .

Physical measurements :

C, H and N were analyzed on a Carlo-Erba 1106 elemental analyzer. Molar conductance was measured on a ELICO (CM82T) conductivity bridge. Magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature on a Gouy balance using $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ as a calibrant. Electron impact mass spectrum was recorded on JEOL-MS Route mass spectrometer. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer FTIR spectrum BX-II spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra was recorded in DMSO- d_6 on Shimadzu UV mini-1240 spectrophotometer.

EPR spectra of the complexes were recorded as polycrystalline sample and at room temperature for Cu^{II} complexes on E_4 -EPR spectrometer using the DPPH as the g-marker.

Results and discussion

Characterization of the ligand (L) :

The EI mass spectra of free ligand (L) confirmed the proposed formula by showing a peak at 558 amu corresponding to the macrocyclic moiety $[(C_{22}H_{24}N_6Br_2)^+]$, calculated atomic mass 560 amu]. It also shows a series of peaks corresponding to various fragments and their intensities give an idea of the stability of the fragments.

There is no band in IR spectrum of the ligand corresponding to free primary diamine and carbonyl group¹⁵ which suggests the complete condensation of the amino group by keto group. A band characteristic of $>C=N$

has appeared at 1596 cm^{-1} . This band confirms the reaction between primary amine group of diamine and carbonyl group of diketone. IR spectrum of the ligand also show the band appearing in the region 1456 cm^{-1} corresponding to the N atom of pyridine ring. On complexation the position of band appearing at 1456 cm^{-1} corresponding to pyridine nitrogen is not shifted. It indicates non-involvement of pyridine nitrogen in coordination¹⁶. The shifting of the $>C=N$ bands towards lower side in the complexes indicates that the coordination takes place through the nitrogen of $C=N$ group, implying that the ligand is tetradentate.

Characterization of the complexes :

On the basis of elemental analysis, the complexes were assigned to possess the composition as shown in Table 1. The molar conductance measurements of the complexes in DMSO, correspond to be non-electrolyte. These complexes may be formulated as $[M(L)X_2]$ [$M = Ni^{II}$ and Cu^{II} ; $X = Cl^-$, NO_3^- and $1/2SO_4^{2-}$].

In the infra-red spectra of the nitrate complexes, the presence of three medium intensity bands in the region $1440\text{--}1460$, $1301\text{--}1323$, $980\text{--}1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to the ν_3 , ν_2 and ν_1 respectively. These suggest the coordinated behaviour of both the nitrate groups with the central metal ion in unidentate manner^{17,18}

The sulphate complexes show two absorption bands ν_1 lies in the range $980\text{--}985\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and ν_3 which splits into two bands present in the region $1140\text{--}1144\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1043\text{--}1120\text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggest the unidentate nature^{19,20} of sulphate group.

Magnetic moment and electronic spectral studies :

The measured magnetic moments of the chloride and nitrate complexes of Ni^{II} at room temperature lie in the

Table 1. Elemental analysis data of the complexes

Complexes	Colour	Molar conductance ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	M.p. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis (%) :			
					Found (Calcd.)			
					C	H	N	M
[Cu(L)Cl ₂]	Black	11.10	284	68	39.27 (39.47)	3.89 (3.83)	11.56 (11.51)	8.72 (8.70)
[CuC ₂₄ H ₂₈ N ₆ Br ₂ Cl ₂]								
[Cu(L)SO ₄]	Dark brown	11.62	294	60	35.69 (35.56)	3.25 (3.45)	10.49 (10.37)	7.60 (7.84)
[CuC ₂₄ H ₂₈ N ₆ SO ₄ Br ₂]								
[Cu(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	Brown	11.40	> 300	62	35.86 (35.92)	3.69 (3.49)	10.48 (10.47)	7.94 (7.92)
[CuC ₂₄ H ₂₈ N ₆ O ₆ Br ₂]								
[Ni(L)Cl ₂]	Light green	5	284	65	36.08 (36.09)	3.48 (3.50)	10.54 (10.52)	7.35 (7.36)
[NiC ₂₄ H ₂₈ N ₆ Br ₂ Cl ₂]								
[Ni(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	Light green	8	270	68	33.84 (33.85)	3.26 (3.29)	9.86 (9.87)	6.87 (6.89)
[NiC ₂₄ H ₂₈ N ₆ O ₆ Br ₂]								
[Ni(L)SO ₄]	Mehandi green	3	278	58	32.63 (32.62)	3.16 (3.17)	10.19 (10.20)	6.64 (6.64)
[NiC ₂₄ H ₂₈ N ₆ O ₄ Br ₂]								

range 2.98–3.00 BM. The electronic spectra of the chloride and nitrate complexes of Ni^{II} exhibit three absorption bands in the range 10526–10741, 16150–18621 and 24752–28409 cm⁻¹. Thus these bands may be assigned to the spin allowed transitions ²1,22; ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{2g}(F) (ν₁), ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{1g}(F) (ν₂) and ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{1g}(P) (ν₃) respectively. The position of these bands indicates that the complexes can have octahedral geometry around the Ni²⁺ ions.

The sulphate complex of Ni^{II} is diamagnetic. Therefore square-planar geometry may be suggested. The electronic spectra of the sulphate complex of Ni^{II} with the ligand show three absorption bands at 13717, 21205 and 25063 cm⁻¹ which correspond to square-planar geometry. These bands may be assignable to the ¹A_{1g}(D) → ¹A_{2g}(G), ¹A_{1g}(D) → ¹B_{2g}(G), ¹B_{1g}(D) → ¹E_g(G) transitions, respectively.

The magnetic moment measurements of the Cu^{II} complexes lie in the range of 1.98–2.01 BM corresponding to one unpaired electron. Electronic spectra of the chloride and nitrate complexes of Cu^{II} complexes display three absorption bands in the range 10718–11210, 18149–18622 and 28169–32362 cm⁻¹. These bands may be assigned to the following transitions; ²B_{1g} → ²A_{1g} (d_{x²-y²} → d_{z²}) (ν₁), ²B_{1g} → ²B_{2g} (d_{x²-y²} → d_{zy}) (ν₂) and ²B_{1g} → ²E_g (d_{x²-y²} → d_{zy}, d_{yz}) (ν₃).

The spectroscopic studies suggest that the spectral features are characteristic of axial geometry and tetragonally elongated geometry. Since the sulphate group coor-

dinate to the Cu²⁺ ion in a monodentate manner, a penta coordinated geometry i.e. trigonal bipyramidal/square pyramidal, may be suggested to this complexes. The sulphate complex with ligand, under study, display two d-d transition bands in the range of 16779 and 24690 cm⁻¹, which may be assigned to the transitions, ²B₁ → ²A₁ and ²B₁ → ³E₁ respectively. Thus this complexes may possess either square pyramidal or trigonal bipyramidal geometry. However, it is not possible to differentiate between these two geometries on the basis of electronic spectra. Hence it is distinguished on the basis of EPR spectra.

The chloride and nitrate complexes of Cu^{II} complexes exhibit anisotropic EPR spectra characteristic of tetragonal copper. The analysis of spectra give g_{||} = 2.1548–2.1755, g_⊥ = 2.0506–2.0568. The observed g_{||} values for the complexes are less than 2.3 which is in agreement with the covalent character of the metal ligand bond. The trend g_{||} > g_⊥ > 2.0023 observed for the complexes indicates that the unpaired electron is localized in d_{x²-y²} orbital of the Cu^{II} ion and the spectral features are characteristic of axial symmetry. Tetragonally elongated structures are confirmed for the Cu^{II} complexes. G = (g_{||} - 2)/(g_⊥ - 2), which measures the exchange interaction between the metal centers in a polycrystalline solid and has been calculated. According to Hathaway²³ if G > 4 the exchange interaction is negligible, but G < 4 indicates considerable exchange interaction in the solid complexes. In the complexes, G values are < 4 indicating the considerable exchange interaction in solid complex (Table 3).

Table 2. Magnetic moment and electronic spectral data of the complexes

Complex	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	λ_{max} (cm ⁻¹)
[Cu(L)Cl ₂]	2.01	10718, 18622, 32362
[Cu(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	2.00	11210, 18149, 28169
[Cu(L)SO ₄]	1.98	16779, 24690
[Ni(L)Cl ₂]	3.00	10741, 18621, 28409
[Ni(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	2.98	10526, 16150, 24752
[Ni(L)SO ₄]	Diamagnetic	13717, 21205, 25063

Table 3. EPR spectral data of the complexes

	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	g_{obs}	G
[Cu(L)Cl ₂]	2.1755	2.0568	2.0963	3.0897
[Cu(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	2.1548	2.0506	2.0853	3.0592
	g_1	g_2	g_3	R
[Cu(L)SO ₄]	2.1318	2.0940	2.0543	1.0503

EPR spectra of sulphate of Cu^{II} complexes provide a very good support to distinguish between these two ground states. For system with $g_3 > g_2 > g_1$, the ratio²⁴ $(g_2 - g_1)/(g_3 - g_2)$, hereafter called the parameter 'R', is very useful for this purpose. If the ground state is predominantly d_{z^2} , the value of R is greater than one. The calculated values of the g_1 , g_2 , g_3 and R are given in Table 3. The sulphate complex with ligand shows the value of R 1.0503 (> 1). It indicates that the sulphate complex has square pyramidal geometry.

Ligand field parameters :

Various ligand field parameters have been calculated for Ni^{II} complexes. The value of B for a given complex can be calculated as,

$$B = (v_2 + v_3 - 3v_1)/15$$

In Ni^{II} complexes, the value of Racah parameter B is found less than the value of free ion i.e. 1041 cm⁻¹. The Nephelauxetic parameter β has been calculated by the help of relation, $\beta = B_{\text{complex}}/B_{\text{free ion}}$. The value of β for Ni^{II} complexes under study, lie in the range 0.60–0.95 (Table 4). These values indicate the appreciable covalent character of metal ligand σ bond.

Table 4. Ligand field parameters of Ni^{II} complexes

Complex	Dq (cm ⁻¹)	B (cm ⁻¹)	β	LFSE (kJ mol ⁻¹)
[Ni(L)Cl ₂]	1074	987	0.95	154
[Ni(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	1052	622	0.60	151

Biological activity :

The ligand (L) and its complexes were evaluated against different species of bacteria and several plant pathogenic fungi^{25–30}. The ligand and its complexes were mixed directly at different concentration as 250, 125, 63.5 $\mu\text{mg ml}^{-1}$. At concentration 250 $\mu\text{mg ml}^{-1}$ ligand and its complexes show better antibacterial and antifungal screening (Tables 5a and 5b). It has been observed that on comparison with reference to antibiotic and fungicides the com-

Table 5a. Antibacterial screening data of the ligand and its complexes

Compounds	<i>S. lutea</i>			<i>E. coli</i>		
	(conc.) $\mu\text{mg ml}^{-1}$			(conc.) $\mu\text{mg ml}^{-1}$		
	250	125	63.5	250	125	63.5
Ligand	18	10	–	10	–	–
[Ni(L)Cl ₂]	23	22	–	16	8	–
[Ni(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	20	15	–	18	12	6
[Cu(L)Cl ₂]	32	25	12	22	24	8
[Cu(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	30	28	10	20	21	9
Streptomycin (std)	35	26	14	28	20	12

Table 5b. Antifungal screening data of the ligand and its complexes

Compounds	<i>A. niger</i>			<i>A. glaucus</i>		
	(conc.) $\mu\text{mg ml}^{-1}$			(conc.) $\mu\text{mg ml}^{-1}$		
	250	125	63.5	250	125	63.5
Ligand	52.4	30.8	12.5	8.2	2.3	10.2
[Ni(L)Cl ₂]	56.3	48.2	26.9	58.6	52.0	22.2
[Ni(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	58.0	44.2	25.0	64.2	38.0	18.0
[Cu(L)Cl ₂]	88.0	50.2	34.0	71.2	46.2	25.0
[Cu(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	60.2	46.2	29.3	67.0	48.0	29.6
Gentamycin (std)	90.0	76.7	48.9	98.0	80.0	45.9

plexes were found to be more effective than ligands. It is suggested that complexation tends to make the ligand to act as more potent bacterial agent than the free ligand. The antimicrobial activity increases after complexation and chelation reduces the polarity of the central metal ion by partial sharing of its positive charge with the donor groups increasing lipophilic nature of the central atom which increase permeability across the lipid membrane³¹.

The antibacterial action of the ligand and the complexes of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} was checked by disc diffusion technique. This was done on *Sarcina lutea* (Gram-positive) and *Escherichia coli* (Gram-negative) bacteria at 30 °C. DMSO was used as a control and Gentamycin as a

standard drug. The results of this study show maximum inhibition by the Cu^{II} complexes.

Aspergillus niger and *Aspergillus glaucus* fungi were used as the test organism for the purpose of antifungal screening by agar plate technique. All the newly synthesized compounds shows considerable inhibition capacity against all the species screened. The results of the antifungal screening are presented in Tables 5a and 5b.

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References

1. Li. R. Moubarake, B. Murray and K. S. Brooke, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2008, 6014.
2. S. Chandra and K. Gupta, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2002, 27, 196.
3. S. Chandra, D. Jain, A. Sarkar and R. Chandra, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 2004, 60, 2411.
4. F. Firdaus, K. Fatima, S. N. Khan, A. U. Khan and M. Shakir, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2008, 33, 467.
5. (a) T. A. Kaden, *Topics Curr. Chem.*, 1984, 121, 54; (b) P. V. Bernhardt and G. A. Lawrance, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1990, 104, 297.
6. T. A. Kaden, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1998, 60, 1117.
7. F. C. J. M. Van Veggel, W. Verboom and D. N. Reinhoudt, *Chem. Rev.*, 1994, 94, 279.
8. K. R. Adam, M. Antolovich, D. S. Baldwin, L. G. Brigden and P. A. Duckworth, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1992, 1869.
9. K. Y. Choi, H. Y. Lee, B. B. Park, J. H. Kim, M. W. Kim, J. W. Ryu, M. Sub and H. Hwan Suh, *Polyhedron*, 2001, 20, 2003.
10. T. W. Hambley, L. F. Lindoy, J. R. Reimers, P. Turner, G. Wei and A. N. W. Cooper, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2001, 614.
11. E. Q. Gao, H. Y. Sun, D. Z. Liao, L. H. Jiang and S. P. Yan, *Polyhedron*, 2002, 21, 359.
12. L. F. Lindoy, "The Chemistry of Macrocyclic Ligand Complexes", Cambridge University Press, UK, 1989.
13. P. Dietrich, P. Viout and J. M. Lehn, "Macrocyclic Chemistry", VCH Publishers Inc., New York, 1993.
14. R. M. Izatt, K. Powak and J. S. Bradshaw, *Chem. Rev.*, 1991, 91, 1721.
15. F. Lions, *Rev. Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1969, 19, 777.
16. S. V. Rosokha, Y. D. Lampeka and I. M. Matoshtan, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1993, 631.
17. P. S. Kalsi, "Spectroscopy of Organic Compounds", 4th ed., New Age International, New Delhi, 2001.
18. R. K. Rao and P. S. Zacharias, *Polyhedron*, 1997, 16, 1201.
19. K. Nakmoto, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley Interscience, New York, 1970.
20. A. B. P Lever, "Crystal Field Spectra, Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", 1st ed., Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968, 249.
21. M. Shakir, O. S. M. Nasman, A. K. Mohamed and S. P. Varkey, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1996, 25, 710.
22. F. Athar, F. Arjmand and S. Tabassum, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2001, 26, 426.
23. A. G. Tomlinson, B. J. Hathway, D. E. Billing and P. Nicholls, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 65.
24. S. Chandra, K. Gupta and S. Sharma, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 2001, 31, 1205.
25. W. G. Hanna and M. M. Moawad, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2001, 26, 644.
26. M. Sakai, A. Hara, S. Anjo and M. Nakamura, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 1999, 18, 1057.
27. P. Kopel, Z. Travnickec, J. Marek, M. Korabik and J. Mrozinski, *Polyhedron*, 2003, 22, 411.
28. S. Chandra and L. K. Gupta, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 2004, 60, 3079.
29. S. Chandra and S. Sharma, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2007, 32, 150.
30. S. Chandra, L. K. Gupta and D. Jain, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 2004, 60, 2411.
31. M. Shakir and S. P. Varkey, *Polyhedron*, 1995, 14, 1117.

